

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most numerous North American bears. The most common is the American black bear, adopted by the brown bear after which the polar bear. Discovered throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. May be darkish or gentle brown (cinnamon), typically even white. Not at all times black in colour. 900,000 and not threatened. □□ Location: The American black bear may be discovered all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Nonetheless, some subspecies such as the Louisiana black bear are protected below the U.S. □□ Measurement: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to 6 ft in size. □□ Features: Most black bears are black, but their fur can vary from dark brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on uncommon events. They've pointed ears and a straight face. Of all the bear species black bears are a few of the most effective at climbing trees. Their comparatively smaller size and shorter claws make them quick and nimble to climb timber for safety, meals, and even hibernation. Nearly all of their food plan is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Food plan: Their varied food regimen gives them the flexibility to dwell in a big range of habitats. Additionally they eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Harmful? They are the more than likely bear to be encountered in the backcountry. And sure, they love honey. The grizzly and Kodiak are the 2 subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are found in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Brown bears are probably the most widespread of all bear species, discovered within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. Grizzlies are accountable for nearly all bear attacks in North America, with 46 per yr. Although their conservation standing is "least concern", their spread-out nature and lowered habitat make most of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a wide number of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a large build, a dish-formed face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the tips, which led to the identify of probably the most famous subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and a few even hunt younger mammals equivalent to elk and moose. Their shade varies from light blonde to darkish brown. The two subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□ Location: Grizzly bears are discovered within the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Dimension: Adults weigh four hundred to 790 pounds, are 6.5 toes lengthy, and have a shoulder peak of 3.3 ft. □□ Weight loss plan: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been known to prey on giant mammals. Coastal grizzlies are typically larger than those found within the Rocky Mountains as a result of a richer weight-reduction plan. Annually there are forty six attacks and 6 deaths. □□ Harmful? Known for their aggressive habits, grizzlies are answerable for essentially the most bear attacks in North America. □□ Location: Kodiak bears are only found on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Measurement: Kodiak bears are almost as massive as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1,400 pounds, 8 toes long, and four toes tall at the shoulder. □□ Weight loss program: Their weight-reduction plan is much like mainland grizzly bears. Nonetheless, resulting from more plentiful food sources, the islands can support a denser bear population. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to grow to be their very own subspecies. This has led to a more advanced social construction which ends up in much less conflict between bears. □□ Dangerous? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears will be aggressive. As a consequence of their isolation, there is just one attack on humans each other year. Largest species of bear on this planet weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Food plan is generally made up of meat, usually from seals. □□ Location: Polar bears are the most important bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. [teddy bear big teddy bear](#) Fur appears white but is actually clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears vary in the snow-lined arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Size: Adult polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and may be 7 to 10 feet tall. They are a threatened species because of loss of habitat from local weather change. Regardless of their huge size polar bears can be fast, sustaining a 6 mph tempo in the water. □□ Options: Compared to different bears, polar bears have a slimmer physique, slender head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps received Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph tempo! □□ Weight loss plan: Their weight-reduction plan consists largely of animals, particularly seals which they'll smell from a mile away. Though they appear white, their fur is definitely clear and their skin is black. □□ Dangerous? Polar bears might be extraordinarily dangerous. They see humans as potential prey. Attacks are uncommon because of the remote nature of their habitat. Identified for its cream colour chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of many smaller bears. Easy to tame and infrequently widespread in circuses. □□ Location: The Asian black bear is present in forests and shrublands across Asia from Iran to Japan. The population is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is taken into account vulnerable. □□ Dimension: One of the smaller species, adults weigh round 300 pounds and stand forty seven to seventy five inches tall. □□ Food plan: Relying on the season it generally feeds on small mammals, birds,

fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses, fruits, berries, seeds, insects, and honey. Assaults on humans are rising as folks encroach on their habitat. ☐☐ Dangerous? They're one in every of the easiest bears to tame (and therefore frequent in circuses), however Asian black bears are extra aggressive than their North American counterparts. Found solely in China. 99% of its eating regimen is bamboo. In actual fact, the second particular person in historical past to obtain a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear while defending his sheep. Recognized for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped physique. ☐☐ Location: Pandas are discovered solely in China. Solely 1,500 to 2,000 stay within the wild and they are thought-about a susceptible species. ☐☐ Measurement: Pandas weigh round 300 pounds and might be over 4 toes tall, a formidable feat considering they weigh only about 3.5 ounces at beginning. It also has an in depth cousin, the Qinling panda which has the identical sample in mild brown and white. ☐☐ Weight loss plan: Not like different bears the panda's diet is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. ☐☐ Features: The large panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped physique. All that fibrous bamboo retains them common: they poop over 40 occasions a day! ☐☐ Harmful? Attacks are uncommon however harmful, provided that pandas have one in every of the highest chunk forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing fifty five to 143 pounds. Found in South East Asia. 8 to 10-inch long tongue for slurping up insects and honey. ☐☐ Location: The Solar bear is discovered within the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It's the least studied bear and. Its population is unsure however considered weak and on the decline on account of lack of habitat and poaching. Solar bears are hunted for their gallbladders and different body parts utilized in traditional medicines. ☐☐ Size: They stand only 39 to fifty five inches and weigh 55 to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. ☐☐ Options: Solar bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a brief snout. They're named for his or her pale, horseshoe-shaped chest patch that looks like a rising solar. In addition they eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. ☐☐ Food plan: Sun bears tear apart bushes and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." In actual fact, they have an incredibly long tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. ☐☐ Dangerous? On account of its shy nature, attacks are rare. Lengthy, shaggy fur and mane gave them the identify sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. ☐☐ Location: The Sloth bear is discovered within the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining inhabitants of less than 20,000, they're considered vulnerable. ☐☐ Measurement: They are 55 to seventy five inches long and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. ☐☐ Features: With their long shaggy fur and mane, they're simple to tell aside from different Asiatic bears. In reality, they're very fast and may out-gallop humans. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging the other way up from timber. They're noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their large curved claws. ☐☐ Weight loss plan: Their food regimen consists of termites, ants, and fruit. ☐☐ Harmful? They are one of the crucial aggressive bears, with the most assaults on humans, mostly because of surprise encounters. They blow the dust round with big puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they can be heard 600 ft away. Sloth bears stand their floor if threatened and do not mix well with rhinos and elephants, often charging at one another when in proximity. Solely South American bear. World's final brief-confronted bear. The identify "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that appear like glasses. This vulnerable species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are discovered in the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. ☐☐ Dimension: They're mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing 47 to seventy nine inches tall. ☐☐ Location: The spectacled bear is the world's last brief-faced bear and the only bear native to South America. ☐☐ Features: The title "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that generally appear like glasses. They spend most of their time in timber where they construct nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard precious fruit and carcasses. ☐☐ Weight-reduction plan: Spectacled bears are largely herbivores with a food plan consisting of largely cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, however they are going to opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. ☐☐ Harmful? Residing in remote mountains, these shy bears stands out as the least harmful of all bear species. Their our bodies are smaller than polar bears but bigger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a uncommon hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that happens in both nature and captivity. Grolar bear habits is nearer to the polar bear. They feature the lengthy necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they have been documented stomping toys, similar to how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably at the London Zoo in 1859, however haven't been confirmed in the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot however DNA exams had been unable to find out what type of bear it was. Adorable koalas are not bears, they are burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears either, they're indestructible, microscopic animals that can survive in area. Most bear assaults occur when a bear is startled or protecting their cubs. Purple pandas? They're in their very own family that are

nearer cousins with skunks and raccoons than bears. 1. BEWARE OF YOUR SURROUNDINGS. Look ahead to bear scat and bear tracks that may indicate a bear is close by, in which case you wish to be additional vigilant. Listed below are a number of ideas you need to use to forestall bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies secure. 2. MAKE NOISE. This helps bears know you are here so they don't accidentally startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack. 3. KEEP YOUR DISTANCE. Whereas you will have nice intentions, a bear is more likely to feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself. 3. Secure YOUR SCENTED Items (AT CAMP). Should you see a bear, don't attempt to strategy or feed it. This contains meals, but additionally your toiletries, for example. Whichever technique you choose, be certain it's a minimum of 200 feet away out of your tent so you do not appeal to bears to your campsite. 4. Keep CALM. In case you meet a bear, don't run. Try to make your self look as massive as possible, waving your arms above your head. You can also extend a jacket above your head to make your self look larger. Lock these things in a bear canister or use a bear bag to cling them up in a tree. Don't scream or try to scare the bear. 5. USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A final RESORT). Speak to it calmly and slowly again away. Full instruction on how to use bear spray here. If the bear is dangerously shut (30 toes) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming barely downward. 6. Fight Back. If all else fails and a bear assaults you, do not play lifeless. Which bear is the most important? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8.Zero to 8.Four toes lengthy, and 4.0 to 5.25 feet tall, the most important bear by each size and weight is the polar bear. The most important ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Fight again with all of your energy and hope that it'll back down. Which bear is probably the most harmful? All bears are dangerous if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is understood for essentially the most attacks. When in bear country, it's all the time smart to hold bear spray. It's nicely deserved, particularly when cubs are round. Each year there are approximately 46 grizzly attacks, 6 resulting in demise. In North America, grizzly bears have probably the most fearsome fame. Which bear is the strongest? Whereas you're most likely to see an American black bear, on common there is just one assault per year. In terms of raw bite power, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's chew reigns supreme. All bears are sturdy and to not be messed with. When using the chunk pressure quotient (chunk power relative to measurement), the sun bear packs essentially the most punch. Initially named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub discovered in the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to escape the fire however sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Quickly after he grew to become an icon and to at the present time is the star of the longest-operating public service announcement marketing campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear known for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. Extra importantly Yogi Bear has inspired numerous through-hikers to attempt to grasp the art of "yogi-ing", the act of not quite begging but receiving favors from strangers. Baloo s a sloth bear, though he has some characteristics of the Asian black bear. He is an easygoing, friendly bear who lives a duty-free lifestyle. He also is perhaps the primary bear to obtain his pilot's license. Earlier than he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son typically would go to on the London Zoo. Winnie is short for "Winnipeg," the city in Canada close to the place he was from. Chris also wrote Learn how to Hike the Appalachian Path. Equal elements backpacking meals and ultralight gear. After through-hiking the Appalachian Path, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to provide quick, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic ideas, guides and how-to's in your inbox each two weeks.

